

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE TECHNIQUES FOR DETACHMENT OF NATURAL STONE BLOCKS FROM THE MASSIF WITH FLEXIBLE HIGH-EXPLOSIVE CHARGES AND BULK-EXPANDING CHEMICAL COMPOSITIONS

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ABSTRACT. Studies of foreign experience in the extraction of magmatic rocks for decorative and cladding purposes show a continuing trend for the use of high-speed explosives in the primary separation of the rock block from the massif. The belief that this is the cheapest way for primary extraction against the background of the prices for cutting of hard and highly abrasive rocks with diamond-rope, chain- and disk-stone cutters, makes quarry owners to put up with the losses from unwanted cracking of high-quality material. The authors undertook a series of experiments on samples of magma rock with hardness $f = 16$ according to Protodyakonov. The advantages and disadvantages of an alternative non-explosive technology for stone splitting with bulk-expanding mixtures were analysed. The results were compared with those using detonating cord charges to detach rock blocks with the same characteristics.

Key words: non-explosive stone splitting, bulk-expanding mixtures, smooth blasting, ornamental stone extrac

Introduction

The products extracted from dimension stone (DS) quarries are prismatic blocks of materials such as granite, gneiss, gabbro, diabase, marble, limestone, sandstone, slates and others. Most of them are preferred because of their aesthetic and attractive characteristics, namely colour, texture, polishability, etc.

Dimension stone blocks are mainly used in the building, making of sculptures and monumental tombstones or ornamental facing materials for interior and exterior of buildings. The definition of rock facing materials covers rough blocks and finished products, but excludes crushed aggregates or stone dust consumed as raw material or recycled for the production of artificial stone.

Four major operations are used in quarries for rock-facing materials: removal of overburden and development of quarrying faces, primary extraction of lamellas, splitting of blocks to dimensions for transport and stone processing. Overburden removal, blocks cutting, splitting, handling, and transportation from quarry site to processing plant are known as the major quarrying operations (Abdollahisharif, Bakhtavar, 2009). Overburden and weathered rocks are usually loosened by blasting and can be removed using a dragline, a scraper, a front-end loader and a bull-dozer. After the surface is cleaned, a trench is made and a bench is formed across the width of the quarry. This provides an additional free surface that facilitates the extraction of subsequent blocks until the first horizon extending across the entire width and length of the quarry is seized or until sufficient space is provided to remove another key block opening a second horizon. The upper surface and the slope of the bench provide two free surfaces (upper and front of the prismatic block). Three additional cuts (surfaces) are made, which define the edges and the back. Those cutting surfaces are usually made with more precise cutting and splitting devices. Capital and operational costs and quarry life are influenced by the method employed for the extraction of dimension stones. Therefore, the selection process of an extraction method is a crucial problem in dimension stone quarries. Below those extraction methods are considered which can separate the desired blocks from the face intact rock (Bakhtavar et al., 2012). For this purpose, diamond wire cutters, chain stone cutters,

blade diamond stone cutters, burners, water jet cutters, smooth blasting, and expansive mixtures are usually used.

The compressive strength of volcanic rocks in Bulgarian quarries of rock facing materials, where field experiments were performed, range from 130 MPa to 300 MPa. The dimensions of the extracted blocks are usually 1.2 - 2 m wide, 1.5 - 3 m long and thick to the nearest split plane. The blocks are separated manually using chisels and hammer to obtain the size and shape of the product sought. During the process of manual separation and sizing, about 50 - 75% of the stone is turned into waste. Because of this reason improved technologies for extraction are needed to reduce the formation of waste in DS mining. In small quarries for volcanic rocks, where a cutting machine cannot be used, controlled cracking in the desired direction by blasting, with minimal damage to the valuable material, is the main technique established after the 1980s (Dino, Cavallo, 2014).

Each unwanted crack in the dimension stone divide it into small pieces as waste or turns it into product with very low value (Muhammad, 2012). Therefore, finding an improved blasting technique in the extraction of stone blocks is of paramount importance. Given these aspects, tests for the formation and development of macro-cracks in the desired direction are carried out in dimension stone quarries, while preventing the unwanted appearance of micro-cracks in the extracted block and the residual rock. In the present research work the analysis was made on the basis of field tests.

Theoretical foundations

The explosive energy released in the rock, in addition to performing useful work of fragmentation and displacement, can cause damage to the residual array in the form of unwanted cracks at the micro-level (Mollova, 2019b). Significant efforts have been made in recent years to investigate and minimise blast damage in conventional blasting operations (Belin, Mollova, 2021). The work on estimating the extent of the damage to the stone is very scarce. These damages should be reduced in the extraction of natural stones, where a small amount of explosive energy is used for primary separation from rocks or for splitting of separated blocks. In some situations, such as contour blasting, digging tunnels and underground chambers, unwanted damage must also be kept to a minimum.

Controlled blasting is useful for the long-term stability of underground workings. Well-planned contour blasting indirectly reduces excavation costs in addition to stability (Zhang, Chang, 1999).

The overhangs in the ceiling and the walls of the underground chambers and tunnels require a large amount of fasteners and reinforcement. Cracking and damage to the residual rock can lead to safety problems due to the collapse of stones, as well as to additional costs incurred to maintain the layers (Mollova, Penev, 2020).

The degree of damage is not only a function of the explosive-seismic impact, but is also related to other site-specific parameters such as rock strength and geological structural characteristics (Zhang, Chang, 1999). The cracking of the rocks creates an imbalance in the energy distribution of the explosion (Singh, 2005). The presence of joints also affects the attenuation of stress waves (Mollova, 2019a). In addition, the presence of clay material in the cracks, its potential for swelling and thickness contribute to the poor quality of the rock mass, which in various situations can lead to excessive fragmentation or slight cracking. As a result of the presence of cracks in the stone blocks, the recovery from the sold product decreases.

All controlled blasting techniques such as cushion-blasting, pre-splitting and smooth blasting have one common goal, namely to better distribute the energy delivered to the rock mass during the detonation of the explosive, so as to control the effects of crushing and breaking (Penev, Mollova, 2020). They are used in blasting operations for extraction of ores and aggregates, when unwanted cracking in the main massif must be avoided. But these techniques develop micro-level cracks that are not desirable in the extraction of rock facing materials (Zhang, Chang, 1999). For this reason, flexible linear decoupled charges with a strongly reduced concentration of high explosive are used for the cleavage of dimension stone blocks. In the second half of the 20th century, the practice required the use of detonating cords (DC) as convenient for work flexible extended charges for detachment. Manufacturers offer DC with different power, determined by the content (weight) of pentaerythritol tetranitrate (PETN) per linear meter of cord. The correct sizing of the charge in relation to the diameter and length of the blast holes is crucial for the presence or absence of random radial cracks and for the controlled displacement of the separated rock mass (Koprev, 2016). Another factor in reducing parasitic cracks is the centring of the charge in the blast hole, which prevents it from touching its walls (Cardu et al., 2005). It is essential to avoid even very small irreversible deformations along the blast holes by the presence of a stemming or damping material around the DC threads in the holes (Koprev, 2012).

To protect the most expensive decorative-facing rock materials from the formation of micro-cracks, in the primary extraction from the massif (as well as in the secondary splitting of the block), instead of explosive impact, controlled cracking with volume-expanding chemical compositions is applied (Muhammad, A., 2012). In recent years, this technology is used in the extraction of marble, breccia, granite and other rocks with high hardness and good cleavage. The method is ineffective in soft rocks. The technology is based on the property of certain chemical compounds to "absorb" water when wet by binding it to their own molecules in the so-called chelating complexes. Upon drying of the material, the water molecules appear to be part of the crystal lattice of the compound. This leads to a drastic increase in the coefficient of volumetric expansion (Stoycheva,

2019). Thus, these substances, when placed in drilled holes and in contact with water, are able to harden and expand after some time, creating stresses in the rocks up to 40-45 MPa. The essence of the technology is the same as in the drilling-wedge and drilling-blasting method. Vertical and horizontal holes are perforated along the contours of the block with the drilling mechanisation (jack-hammers, jumbos or drills). The effective range is from $\varnothing$ 32 to $\varnothing$ 55 mm. At smaller diameters, the percentage of volumetric expansion is insufficient to develop destructive stresses. With larger diameters, the cost of materials becomes inexpedient against the background of the useful effect. According to the literature, the distance between the holes depends on their diameter, the specific conditions, the type of rocks extracted, and the expandability of the chemical compound. Some manufacturers claim that as the depth of the holes increases, the distance between them can increase. The stronger the rock, the smaller the distance between the perforations. Most often the distances between the holes are from 100 to 400 mm, and the free surface 400 to 600 mm. The depth of the holes is from 2/3 to 3/4 and in very rare cases equal to the full size of the block. The height of the bench with this technology is relatively small - up to 2.5 m. When the benches are higher, the separation of the blocks takes place in stages from the half-steps. The time for destruction of the rocks (splitting takes place along the line of drilling holes) varies from 10 to 24 hours, and factors influencing this time are: the type of chemicals used, the properties of the rocks and the temperature of the environment and the rocks. The time for splitting the rocks can be reduced by shortening the distance between the holes, but this in turn increases the time and cost of drilling operation. It is possible to separate very large blocks from the array with a volume of up to 2000 m³. Rock-breaking stresses could form macro-cracks not exceeding the diameter of the holes. Powdered substances are available, packed in plastic bags to protect from humidity. The powdered material is mixed with 20 to 40% water and the resulting slurry is poured into the holes. Chemical reactions begin immediately. The expanding mixture exerts the same pressure in each hole and the block separates in the direction of the drilled holes. This technology for extraction of rock blocks is most often applied in combined ways of making vertical longitudinal sections (cuts), as the volume of drilling works is reduced by 30 to 40% compared to the drilling-wedge method. Products from different manufacturers are available on the market. The principle of action and the main ingredients are identical, the differences being in the additives for speeding up and stabilising the process. A specific feature is the temperature range for efficient operation of these compositions. Below 0 °C the water freezes and the technology becomes inapplicable. As the temperature rises, the chemical processes accelerate and the efficiency increases. At temperatures above 30 °C the reaction becomes violent and the risk of accidents increases.

Experimental part

The tests for assessment of damages caused by compressive stresses were performed in quarries for extraction of volcanic rocks for decorative - monumental purposes with a Protodyakonov hardness coefficient $f = 16$. To compare the effects of the impacts, it was necessary to conduct tests under approximately the same conditions.

For the comparative analysis the authors made two groups of experiments:

1. Cleavage of stone blocks by blasting holes:
 - with different mass of the linear charge;
 - with different filling of the residual space between the charge and the walls of the blast hole;
 - using a centrally fixed detonating cord.
2. Splitting of stone blocks by filling drilled holes with a volume-expanding chemical mixture.

Cleavage of rock blocks by blasting

Four tests were performed for the first group of experiments. Approximately the same rock formations with three open surfaces and a joint on the fourth side or with four open surfaces were selected for each experiment. The selected rock bodies had widths along the splitting strip of about 1.5 m at a height of the desired gap of about 2.0 m. Thus, we achieved almost the same dimensions of the cutting areas of about 3 m². Three parallel vertical blast holes with a length of 1.80 m and a diameter of $\varphi = 36 \div 42$ mm were drilled in each of the four rocks. The distance between the blast holes was about 0.40 m so that the value of the compressive stresses in the collision zone between two adjacent charges was sufficient to form perpendicular tensile stresses to form a connecting crack between the holes. The distance of the peripheral holes to the free sides was 0.35 m. Under the influence of the reflected pressure waves, this crack should continue to propagate evenly to the open surfaces perpendicular to its plane.

For the purposes of the study, DC with a PETN content of 12 g/m was used. For the preparation of the charges, the DC was divided into equal pieces with a length of 200 cm. Thus, the mass of explosives in each section was 24 g PETN. At one end of each piece, a knot was made to increase the weight of the charge at the bottom of the blast hole and to keep the DC thread stretched along the length of the hole. The average market price per 1 m of used DC with a PETN content of 12 g/m is about 0.5 EUR. The average market price of the used electric detonators with instant action is 1.5 EUR/piece.

To mitigate the shock effect of the high-power blasting charge on the walls of the blast hole, three types of buffer materials were used - air, sand and water gel. The aqueous gel was prepared by swelling a coarse polyacrylate-polyacrylamide copolymer. The idea was to modify the practical impermeability of pure water, as well as to prevent its leakage through cracks.

Experiment - 1: Splitting of a rock piece with a charge of 12 g/m. In each of the three explosive holes a thread of DC was inserted, by pushing the knot to the bottom with the help of a wooden rod. Thus, the amount of charge in one hole was about 22.5 g of PETN (excluding the content of 12 cm DC protruding outside the hole). The first hole was left with an "air stemming", the second was filled with sand around the charge, and the third was filled with water gel. The ends of the three DC-strands were joined with a short section of DC in a common network.

Experiment - 2: Splitting of a rock piece with a charge of 24 g/m. In each of the three explosive holes were placed two strands of DC, inserting the knots to the bottom with the help of a wooden rod. Thus, the amount of charge in one hole was about 45 g PETN (excluding the content of 12 cm DC protruding outside the hole). The first hole was left with an "air stemming", the second was filled with sand around the charge, and the third was filled with water gel. The ends of the three DC-strands were joined with a short section of DC in a common chain.

Experiment - 3: Splitting of a rock piece with a charge of 36 g/m. In each of the three blast holes were placed three strands

of DC, inserting the knots to the bottom with the help of a wooden rod. Thus, the amount of charge in one hole was about 68 g PETN (excluding the content of 12 cm DC protruding outside the hole). The first hole was left with an "air gaps", the second was filled with sand around the charge, and the third was filled with water gel. The ends of the three DC-strands were joined with a short section of DC in a common chain.

Experiment - 4: Splitting of a rock piece with a centralised fixed charge of DC 24 g/m. In each of the three explosive holes we placed two strands of DC, wrapped in a "casing" of corrugated cardboard. Thus, the amount of charge in one hole was about 43 g PETN (excluding the content of 20 cm DC protruding outside the hole). The ends of the three DC-strands were joined with a short section of DC in a common chain.

The initiation of the explosive chains was performed with electric detonators with instantaneous action. To reduce the effect of the air-blast, the exposed parts of the DC network were covered with a thick layer of sifted sand.

Splitting of rock blocks by expanding mixtures

Three attempts were made for the second group of experiments. Untightened (free) boulders of the same type and size were used for each experiment. The selected splitting strips were about 1.5 m long with a stone thickness of about 1.0 m. Thus, we achieved almost the same dimensions of the cutting areas of 1.5 m². The technology uses the same pre-drilled holes in the rock as the blast method. In each of the three stones, parallel vertical holes with a length of 0.80 m and a diameter of $\varphi = 38 \div 42$ mm were drilled in a line.

For Test - 1, five holes were perforated every 0.20 m with a distance of the peripheral holes to the sides of 0.35 m.

For Test - 2, four holes were perforated every 0.30 m with a distance of the peripheral holes to the sides of 0.30 m.

For Test - 3, three holes were perforated at 0.40 m with a distance of the peripheral holes to the sides of 0.35 m.

The composition was unpacked and homogenised with cold water on the site, immediately before use. The ratio used was from 280 to 320 ml of water per 1 kg of dry mix, depending the weather conditions. The finished solution was poured expeditiously directly into the cleaned from dust dry holes. The test boulders were exposed to the chemical expander for the 24 hours prescribed by the supplier and were periodically monitored for changes.

The average market price per 1 kg of the chemical expanding composition used is around EUR 1.75. The average consumption when filling a 1 m hole with a diameter φ 40 mm is about 1.5 kg of dry matter in the form of an aqueous solution. It can be assumed, that the value of the chemical expander consumed per linear meter of perforation (φ 40 mm) is about EUR 2.63.

Results and discussion

The use of flexible linear charges allows for an even distribution of the shock wave and the pressure of the explosive gases along the entire length of the blast hole. Thus, the compressive stresses on the walls of the hole are the same and the chance of forming a crack in an undesirable direction becomes smaller.

In the experimental blasting with a single thread DC 12 g/m (Experiment - 1) a slight crack of the rock body in the intended direction was observed, accompanied by a slight displacement

of the treated block. Due to the low charge and the buffering role of air, sand and water gel, which further reduces the explosive effect on the rock - after the excavation, on the block and the array no parasitic cracks were observed on the chipped surfaces. The value of spent explosives, excluding the cost of drilling and damping water gel was 5 EUR for 3 m² of cut surface (for 7 m DC x 0.5 EUR/m = 3.50 EUR and for 1 electric detonator x 1.5 EUR = 1.5 EUR).

In the experimental blasting with double thread DC 24 g/m (Experiment - 2) a good splitting of the rock body in the intended direction was observed, accompanied by a satisfactory displacement of the treated block. Due to the buffering role of air and sand, no visible cracks were observed on the chipped surface on the block and the array. A slight single crack was observed along the channels remaining from the third hole (with the water gel). A probable reason is the formation of a hydro-shock wave due to the high density of the water gel. The value of spent explosives, excluding the costs of drilling and damping water gel was 8 EUR for 3 m² of cut surface (for 13 m DC x 0.5 EUR/m = 6.50 EUR and for 1 electric detonator x 1.5 EUR = 1.5 EUR).

In the experimental blasting with a triple thread DC 36 g/m (Experiment - 3) there was a serious detachment of the rock body in the intended direction, accompanied by a large displacement of the treated block. Despite the buffering role of air and sand, visible cracks were observed on the chipped surfaces. Longitudinal and radial cracks were seen in the channels remaining from the three holes. The damages were lesser at the first hole (with the air stemming). The value of spent explosives, excluding the costs of drilling and damping water gel was 11 EUR for 3 m² of cutting surface (for 19 m DC x 0.5 EUR/m = 9.50 EUR and for 1 electric detonator x 1.5 EUR = 1.5 EUR).

In the experimental blasting with a centrally fixed charge of DC 24 g/m (Experiment - 4) a very good crack through the rock body in the intended direction was observed, accompanied by sufficient displacement of the treated block. Due to the buffer role of the corrugated cardboard, no visible cracks were observed on the block and the array on the chipped surfaces. The value of the spent explosive materials, excluding the costs for drilling works and centralizers made of corrugated cardboard, was 8 EUR for 3 m² of cutting area (for 13 m DC x 0.5 EUR/m = 6.50 EUR and for 1 electric detonator x 1.5 EUR = 1.5 EUR). Given the satisfactory results achieved by splitting and displacement without visible damage, the authors take this experiment as a milestone in calculating the average value to obtain 1 m² of cutting plane using smooth blasting with a flexible decoupled charge.

During the separation with the volume-expanding composition of Test - 1, a crack was noticed along the line between the flooded holes as early as the sixth hour after filling them with the solution. By the 12th hour the crack had reached a width of 10 to 12 mm. By the 24th hour, a slit crack with a width of 28-30 mm and no distortion had formed. The value of the consumed materials, excluding the costs for drilling works, was EUR 10.50 per 1.5 m² of cut plane. For the filling of 5 holes of 0.8 m each (4.0 m totally), using 1.5 kg/m reagent, 6.0 kg of dry mixture was utilized. The reagent costs 1.75 EUR/kg, so the total was 10.5 EUR.

During the splitting with a volume-expanding composition of Test - 2, a crack was observed along the line between the flooded holes about 10 hours after filling them with the solution.

By the 16th hour, the crack had reached a width of 13 to 15 mm. By the 24th hour, a 24-26 mm wide fissure had formed and distorted due to the presence of a vein. The value of the consumed materials excluding the costs of drilling works was EUR 8.40 per 1.5 m² of cutting plane. For the filling of 4 holes of 0.8 m each (3.2 m totally), using 1.5 kg/m reagent, 4.8 kg of dry mixture was utilized. The reagent costs 1.75 EUR/kg, so the total was 8.40 EUR.

When splitting with a volume-expanding composition of Test - 3, the first crack along the line between the filled holes appeared after the 12th hour of their filling with the solution. By the 20th hour, the crack had reached a width of 10 to 11 mm. By the 24th hour, a gap 18-19 mm wide had formed and distorted due to the presence of a joint. The value of the consumed materials excluding the costs of drilling works was EUR 6.30 per 1.5 m² of cutting area. For the filling of 3 holes of 0.8 m each (2.4 m totally), using 1.5 kg/m reagent, 3.6 kg of dry mixture was utilized. The reagent costs 1.75 EUR/kg, so the total was 6.30 EUR.

Given the equal distance between the perforations compared to the experiments with detonating cord and the achieved satisfactory results of cleavage and displacement without significant damage to the material, the authors take this experiment as orientation in calculating the average value to obtain 1 m² of cutting surface using bulk-expanding chemical reagent.

Conclusions

Based on the proceeded experiments, a comparative analysis of the costs of splitting stone blocks of volcanic origin during their extraction in DS quarries was made, by means of instantaneous explosive action with DC and slow impact with bulk-expanding chemical mixtures. The average value for the formation of a 1.0 m² cutting surface by smooth blasting with a flexible linear charge of DC without the application of visible parasitic cracks on the surfaces of the material amounts to about 2.70 EUR/m². The minimum value for effective formation of 1.0 m² of cut plane by volume-expanding chemical mixture, without causing significant damage to the surfaces of the material was about 4.20 EUR/m².

Splitting of rock blocks with detonating cord is the fastest and cheapest method for extraction and secondary processing of dimension stones, but the risk of damage with micro-cracks continues to affect the performance of the final products. Due to the high performance of PETN charges, the relative cost of drilling can be reduced by increasing the distance between the bore-holes. This will contribute to even higher economic efficiency of blasting activities. The results of the experimental blastings show that additional research and field tests are needed to improve the control over the distribution of explosive energy to concentrate the compressive stresses in the desired direction, namely between the perforations along the breakaway loop. In practice, this will lead to an increase in the efficiency of the charges from the DC.

The main advantage of expanding mixtures (despite their higher cost) over explosive energy methods is the simplified unlicensed acquisition, transportation, storage and use. Another advantage of the technology for rock splitting with bulk-expanding compositions is the negligible danger of formation of micro-cracks in the decorative stones. Additional advantage of this methodology is the lack of need for expensive equipment

and certified qualified personnel for its implementation. The main disadvantages are the slow action and the narrow temperature interval for work. When optimising the processes, the methodology has the potential to replace blasting activities in the extraction of expensive magmatic rocks near protected sites.

The authors are planning to continue their research in the following areas:

- testing of charges from DC with axial fixation in the blast hole in the housing for directing the explosive energy, with stemming to seal the space between charge and walls of the hole;
- testing of DC charges with axial fixation in blast holes with local slots (notches) for directing the split in the desired direction. Pre-cutting the walls of the blast hole would increase the stress concentration in the area, and it is expected that the crack should start from the notched area.
- application of technology with expanding chemical compositions in the primary separation of rock blocks from the main massif.

References

- Abdollahisharif J., Bakhtavar E., 2009. An intelligent algorithm of minimum cutting plane to find optimal size of extractable-blocks in dimension stone quarries, *Archives of Mining Sciences*, 54 (4), 641-656.
- Bakhtavar E., Abdollahisharif J., Lotfi E., Oraee K., Assessment of parameters influencing the extraction method selection for the dimension stone quarries, *Proceedings of SME Annual Meeting: Mine to Market, Now it's Global*, Feb. 19-22, 2012, Society for Mining, Metallurgy & Exploration, Seattle, WA, 244-248.
- Belin V. A., Mollova Z. G., 2021. Influence of the type of donor charges on the detonation rate of low-sensitivity explosives, *Sustainable Development of Mountain Territories*, 1 (47), 112-119.
- Cardu M., Patrucco M., Lovera E., Michelotti E., Quarrying by explosive and diamond wire in hard dimension stones, *Proceedings of the European Federation of Explosives Engineers, Brighton Conference 2005*, 409 – 414.
- Dino G. A., Cavallo A., 2014. Ornamental stones of the Verbano Cusio Ossola quarry district: Characterization of materials, quarrying techniques and history and relevance to local and national heritage, in: *Global Heritage Stone: Towards International Recognition of Building and Ornamental Stones*, Geological Society of London Special Publication SP 407 (1).
- Koprev I. 2012. Otkrit dobiv na skalni blokove, *Avangard Prima*, (in Bulgarian).
- Koprev I. 2016. Tehnologiya na dobiva na skalno-oblitsovachni materiali, *Avangard Prima*, (in Bulgarian).
- Mollova Z., Penev V., 2020. Control of blast-induced seismic action generated by technological blastings, *Sustainable extraction and processing of raw materials journal*, 1, 64-67.
- Mollova Z., 2019a. Blast load analysis and effect on building structures, *Journal of Mining and Geological Sciences*, 2, 70-75.
- Mollova Z., 2019b. New insights into the impact of blast wave on the human body, *Journal of Mining and Geological Sciences*, 2, 75-81.
- Muhammad A., 2012. M.Sc. Thesis, Extraction of marble block using cracking powder. University of Engineering and Technology, Peshawar.
- Penev V., Mollova Z., 2020. Design optimization of drilling and blasting operations: A case study on copper ore mining in Asarel, *Journal of mining and geological sciences*, 63, 84-89.
- Singh S. P., 2005. Blast Control Damage in Jointed Rock Mass. *International Journal of Fragblast*, 9 (3), 175- 183.
- Stoycheva N., 2019. M.Sc. Thesis, Analiz na metodite zan dobiv na skalno-oblitsovachni materiali i predlozhenie za vnedryavane na novo pokolenie nedetonirashti eksplozivni University of mining and geology, Sofia, (in Bulgarian).
- Zhang J. C., Chang C., On damage mechanism of micro crack zone in rock blasting and its measurements, *Proceedings of 6th Int. Symp. Rock fragmentation by blasting, FRADBLAST-6*, August 8-10, 1999, The South African Inst. of Mining and Metall., Johannesburg, 358 -368.